

Gestures and Early Words in Typically Developing Indian Children

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Abstract

Background: Children develop pre-language and nonverbal skills from birth, which serve as precursors to the development of linguistic skills. Before beginning to use verbal language, infants predominantly use gestures and non-verbal behaviors to express their wants and desires. This study will aim at scrutinizing the development of gestures and verbal language in Tamil speaking infants exhibiting typical development from 10 months to 12 months.

Methods: A pilot study with convenient sampling was considered with a sample size of 30 participants. The coding of the child's gestures and verbal behavior was carried out using ELAN Software

Results: Expressive gestures were the most common, followed by metaphoric gestures across the three months. Beat gestures were found to emerge only from 12 months of age. Children's verbal expressive language development is still emerging, with only 10% displaying meaningful words by 11 months and 40% by 12 months, with no significant gender differences. The analysis depicted a statistically significant correlation between expressive gestures and metaphoric gestures with verbal behaviors.

Conclusion: Children exhibit a variety of gestures and verbal behaviors between 10 to 12 months of age such as laryngeal grunting, vocalizations, imitative words, and non-meaningful words. Understanding how gestures, early words, and verbal conduct affect a child's language development, can assist prepare children with special needs for training as well as early developmental problem detection.

Keywords: Gestures, Verbal Behaviors, Language Development, Communication, Vocalizations, India

Introduction

Language development begins early in human life, with infants starting without knowing a language and later distinguishing speech sounds by ten months of age. Pre-language and nonverbal skills, such as gestures, facial expressions, imitation, joint attention, eye contact, emotions, and feelings, support language development and learning (1). Infants use gestures and non-verbal behaviors to express wants and desires before verbal language (2). Infants as young as 9-12 months can express intentions using whole body signals and hand

movements (1). Language development in children follows a pattern of interactive, gestural, pragmatic, play, and attachment skills. Language input from parents significantly predicts children's later language development (3, 4). In addition to using words, elders also produce gestures when they are around their kids (5, 6). Therefore, gestural input is also related to development of later language skills in children (7, 8). Gestures play a crucial role in a child's linguistic development, as they serve as a precursor to speech at every stage of development (6). Adults and parents provide models for children to learn gesture styles and

combinations, modifying their gestures to communicate effectively. Variabilities in gesture production can be observed in both isolation and combination with speech (9). Children use various gestures to communicate their needs and desires, including expressive, instrumental, enactive, and deictic gestures. These gestures can be classified into ritual, deictic, and symbolic gestures (10). Ritual gestures involve repetitive motor movements, while iconic gestures are closely related to speech semantics (11). Metaphoric gestures represent abstract concepts, while deictic gestures indicate objects or items by pointing with the hand or finger. Beat gestures are rhythmic movements that stress or place emphasis on certain words or phrases, with two phases of movements, such as in/out and up/down.

Gesture is a pervasive human behavior that impacts communication, problem-solving, and thinking (12). Children communicate intentionally between eight to nine months of age using gestures, with pointing being a common form. This allows children to communicate even before developing verbal language capacities and can be used to manage others' behavior. The production of gestures is influenced by motor skills development, with reaching gestures appearing frequently in the first year of life and pointing gestures increasing at 16 to 20 months. Verbal language use to name objects generally begins two to three months after the development of pointing gestures. Children produce gestures along with vocal behaviour before producing two-word combinations (13). Adult caretakers usually combine pointing gestures and verbal productions while communicating and naming items in the child's environment. Infants at around the age of one year begin combining forms of gesture and word based on the model and experiences in the environment and use them (14). Gestures and speech communicate meaning through different mechanisms, with gestures providing a holistic and global meaning and speech more discreetly using words and grammar units (10, 15). Gestures can convey a child's thoughts, even those that the child does not communicate verbally.

Infants imitate adult speech using vocalizations, starting at 10-13 months and spontaneous speech between 12-18 months (16-18). Early words are predominantly nouns with a bisyllabic CVCV syllable structure (18). From birth, infants involve maximum during parent interaction and the early language of the child increases because of the interaction.

Need for the Study

Gestures are visuospatial events used in communication and are influenced by individual thoughts, language processing, and cultural backgrounds. Although research suggests that children

use gestures independent of verbal behaviour, there is limited research on how language and gesture develop in children, especially within the Indian scenario. Adults use hand and arm gestures a great deal of the time when speaking, but little is known about how young children use gestures in relation to speech. For e.g., children point before they talk, and some children are reported to use more gestures than speech at the age of 24 months (19). In Tamil speaking children, early words emerge between 11-13 months of age, but no published data exists on gesture use. This study aims to study the development of gestures and verbal language in Tamil speaking infants exhibiting typical development.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was to observe and analyse the development of gestures and early words in typically developing children. The specific objectives were as follows:

1. To observe the presence of gestures in children between 10 and 12 months of age
2. To describe the verbal behaviours in children between 10 and 12 months of age
3. To compare the frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour across ages and gender
4. To analyse correlation, if any, between presence of gestures and verbal behaviour in children between 10 and 12 months of age

Methods

The study analyzed the development of gestures and early words in typically developing children aged 10, 11, and 12 months, selected from a multispeciality private hospital in Chennai, India, using a pilot study with 30 participants.

Inclusion Criteria

Only those who met the following criteria were included in this study:

1. No reported concerns regarding child's motor, sensory and social development
2. Normal hearing function (Pass hearing screening based on transient evoked otoacoustic emissions using Otodynamics Otoport lite equipment)
3. Normal receptive and expressive language development [Age appropriate development on ComDeall Developmental Checklist (20)]
4. Exposed to Tamil as the primary language for communication

Table 1. Summary of participant demographics

Parameters	10 months	11 months	12 months
No. of Males	5	5	5
No. of Females	5	5	5
Maternal Age (in years)	25.30 ± 0.823	27.00 ± 0.471	30.10 ± 4.581
Maternal Occupation			
Unemployed	7	3	7
Semi-Skilled	-	-	1
Semi Professional	1	-	1
Skilled Worker	-	1	-
Professional	2	6	1
Mother's Education			
High School	-	1	2
Diploma	1	-	1
Graduate	8	6	4
Post Graduate	1	3	3
Paternal Age	29.40 ± 0.966	32.30 ± 1.160	37.00 ± 3.651
Father's Occupation			
Semi-Skilled	2	1	2
Semi Professional	-	2	-
Skilled worker	-	4	4
Professional	8	3	4
Father's Education			
High School	2	1	1
Diploma	-	1	1
Graduate	3	4	3
Post Graduate	5	4	5
Family Structure			
Joint Family	2	3	2
Nuclear Family	8	7	8

Table 2. Details of Socio-Economic Status of the participants

Parameters	10 months	11 months	12 months
Upper	2	2	2
Upper Middle	6	4	2
Lower Middle	-	3	5
Upper Lower	2	1	1
Lower	-	-	-

Table 3. Presence of gestures in children between 10 and 12 months of age

Variables	N	10 months		11 months		12 months	
		Mean %	SD	Mean %	SD	Mean %	SD
Expressive Gestures	10	42.27	10.62	41.87	8.34	33.52	9.61
Instrumental Gestures	10	4.17	5.53	7.36	5.83	2.82	4.32
Deictic Gestures	10	2.88	4.89	2.53	5.02	5.31	9.91
Iconic Gestures	10	2.95	5.59	2.97	3.10	8.04	11.18
Beat Gestures	10	0	0	0	0	0.13	0.43
Metaphoric Gestures	10	34.53	10.46	31.32	7.26	31.49	12.58
Verbal Behaviour	10	13.16	8.03	13.92	11.18	18.65	12.61

Table 4. Description of verbal behaviours in children between 10 and 12 months of age

Verbal Behaviours	10 months		11 months		12 months	
	Mean %	SD	Mean %	SD	Mean %	SD
Laryngeal grunting	46.91	34.96	60.60	32.52	30.00	34.01
Vocalizations	41.00	36.74	21.79	16.00	11.03	13.58
Imitative words	5.42	10.77	3.73	7.11	15.91	20.72
Non-meaningful words	6.67	15.74	13.30	17.62	36.65	28.60
Meaningful words	0.00	0.00	0.59	1.86	6.41	14.51

Table 5. Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour across age

Annotations	Age	N	Mean	SD	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min	Max	Z -Value (p-Value)
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
Expressive Gesture	10	10	42.27	10.62	34.67	49.87	25.56	59.38	4.281 (0.118)
	11	10	41.87	8.34	35.90	47.84	23.47	52.33	
	12	10	33.52	9.61	26.64	40.40	23.53	50.50	
	Total	30	39.22	10.10	35.45	42.99	23.47	59.38	
Instrumental Gestures	10	10	4.17	5.53	.21	8.13	.00	15.96	4.623 (0.099)
	11	10	7.36	5.83	3.19	11.54	.00	19.77	
	12	10	2.82	4.32	-.26	5.92	.00	14.38	
	Total	30	4.79	5.44	2.75	6.82	.00	19.77	
Deictic Gestures	10	10	2.88	4.89	-.61	6.38	.00	14.81	1.317 (0.518)
	11	10	2.53	5.02	-1.06	6.13	.00	16.33	
	12	10	5.31	9.91	-1.78	12.40	.00	32.41	
	Total	30	3.57	6.88	1.00	6.14	.00	32.41	
Iconic Gestures	10	10	2.95	5.59	-1.04	6.95	.00	17.39	1.146 (0.564)
	11	10	2.97	3.10	.74	5.19	.00	9.78	
	12	10	8.04	11.18	.04	16.04	.00	27.94	
	Total	30	4.65	7.58	1.82	7.48	.00	27.94	
Beat Gestures	10	10	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	2.000 (0.368)
	11	10	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	
	12	10	.13	.43	-.17	.45	.00	1.38	
	Total	30	.04	.25	-.048	.14	.00	1.38	
Metaphoric Gestures	10	10	34.53	10.46	27.05	42.02	19.23	53.61	0.914 (0.633)
	11	10	31.32	7.26	26.12	36.51	20.93	48.05	
	12	10	31.49	12.57	22.49	40.49	13.59	53.62	
	Total	30	32.45	10.08	28.68	36.21	13.59	53.62	
Verbal Behaviour	10	10	13.16	8.03	7.41	18.91	1.06	31.11	1.210 (0.546)
	11	10	13.92	11.18	5.92	21.92	1.30	30.61	
	12	10	18.65	12.61	9.63	27.67	.00	36.89	
	Total	30	15.24	10.69	11.25	19.24	.00	36.89	

Table 6. Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviours between genders

Annotations	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Z	P
Expressive Gesture	Male	15	40.72	10.24	-0.726	0.468
	Female	15	37.72	10.09		
Instrumental Gestures	Male	15	3.15	3.35	-1.127	0.260
	Female	15	6.42	6.66		
Deictic Gestures	Male	15	2.01	2.94	-0.541	0.589
	Female	15	5.14	9.17		
Iconic Gestures	Male	15	4.63	7.93	-0.064	0.949
	Female	15	4.68	7.48		
Beat Gestures	Male	15	.00	.00	-1.000	0.317
	Female	15	.09	.35		
Metaphoric Gestures	Male	15	33.80	12.18	-0.643	0.520
	Female	15	31.10	7.63		
Verbal Behaviour	Male	15	15.66	9.65	-0.311	0.756
	Female	15	14.82	11.97		

Table 7. Correlation between gestures and verbal behaviours (using Pearson's Correlation)

Annotations	Mean	SD	N	r - Value	p-Value
Expressive Gesture	39.22	10.10	30	- 0.636	0.000 *
Verbal Behaviour	15.24	10.69	30		
Instrumental Gestures	4.79	5.44	30	-0.301	0.105
Verbal Behaviour	15.24	10.69	30		
Deictic Gestures	3.57	6.88	30	-0.030	0.875
Verbal Behaviour	15.24	10.69	30		
Iconic Gestures	4.65	7.58	30	0.244	0.195
Verbal Behaviour	15.24	10.69	30		
Beat Gestures	.046	.251	30	-0.269	0.150
Verbal Behaviour	15.24	10.69	30		
Metaphoric Gestures	32.45	10.08	30	-0.416	0.022 *
Verbal Behaviour	15.24	10.69	30		

Note:* indicates $p < .05$

Figure 1. Correlation between Expressive Gestures and Verbal Behaviors

Figure 2. Correlation between Metaphoric Gestures and Verbal Behaviors

Exclusion Criteria

1. Children with any developmental delay
2. Preterm babies less than 34 weeks
3. Children from non-Tamil speaking families
4. Any reported disabilities for the primary caretaker

Procedure

The study recruited participants from a hospital's Paediatrics outpatient clinic. Informed consent was obtained from parents or caretakers of children who participated in the study. The participant information form was used to gather demographic details, personal data, milestones of the child and details of family using Modified Kuppaswamy's Socioeconomic Status Scale (21). Language sampling involved recording free play sessions between the child and their parent/caretaker at home, encouraging natural interaction and using available toys. The sessions were video-recorded for analysis.

Analysis

The child's free play session with parent/caretaker interaction was recorded and analyzed for observing the appearance of gestures and verbal responses. The coded behaviors included

- Expressive gestures: These gestures are used to express emotions (e.g., clapping, smiling)
- Instrumental gestures: Gestures that are used to control the behaviour of another (e.g., place mother's hand on the lid of the container indicating to open it).
- Enactive/Iconic gestures: These gestures represent actions with some level of symbolism (e.g., pushing away the hand to express the action for enough).
- Deictic gestures: Gestures that are used to point to objects or people (e.g., finger pointing).
- Metaphoric gestures: Gestures depicting an abstract imagery in a concrete form (e.g., keeping hands shaped like a heart next to the chest to indicate love).
- Beat gestures: Gestures represented with hands and arms during conversations (e.g., shaking index finger to say no)
- Verbal behaviours: Orally produced utterances including vocalisations and meaningful words.

The ELAN (EUDICO Linguistic Annotator) Software, developed by Max Planck Institute of Psycholinguists, was used for coding the child's behavior, analyzing

languages, sign languages, and gestures, and creating time-aligned annotations of audio and/or video recordings (22).

Statistical Analysis

The study used SPSS version 16 software to analyze raw data on gestures and verbal behaviors in children. Descriptive statistics (Mean and SD) were used to quantify these behaviors. Kruskal Wallis Test was used to analyse the age related differences in the presence of gestures and verbal behaviours. Mann Whitney U-test was used to analyse the gender related differences in the presence of gestures and early words in infants. Karl Pearson's correlation was used to analyse the correlation between the types of gestures and the presence of verbal behaviours in infants.

Results

The aim of the present study was to analyse the development of gestures and early words in typically developing children. The study was carried out with 30 participants along with their parent/primary caretaker, who were recruited based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The speech and language sampling included a video recording of free play between the child and their respective caretaker. Table 1 summarizes the demographic details of the participants (infants and their caretakers) of this study. Table 2 depicts the socioeconomic status of the participants, as measured using Kuppaswamy's socioeconomic status scale (21).

The analysis of video recording for the presence of gestures and other communicative behaviours was carried out using the ELAN software. The results of the study are presented as follows:

1. Presence of gestures in children between 10 and 12 months of age
2. Description of verbal behaviours in children between 10 and 12 months of age
3. a) Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour across age
b) Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour between genders
4. Correlation between presence of gestures and verbal behaviours in children

Presence of gestures in children between 10 and 12 months of age

The analysis was done to identify the presence of gestures in children between 10 to 12 months of age. Table 3 represents the mean percentage and standard deviation of all gestures between children of 10 and 12 months of age. Results from Table 3 indicates that expressive gestures were the most common followed by metaphoric gestures across the three months. Beat gestures were found to emerge only from 12 months of age.

Description of verbal behaviours in children between 10 and 12 months of age

The verbal behaviours were analysed and further classified into laryngeal grunting, vocalizations, imitative words, non-meaningful words, and true meaningful words. Table 4 represents the description of verbal behaviours in children between 10 and 12 months of age. Meaningful words were not exhibited by children at 10 months and they were seen emerging only by 11 months of age. Only 10% of children exhibited meaningful word by 11 months and 40% by 12 months of age indicating that children are still beginning to learn verbal expressive language.

Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour across age

Analysis was carried out using Kruskal Wallis Test. Table 5 represents the comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour across ages (10, 11 and 12 months). The results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences in the occurrence of gestures and verbal behaviours across the age of 10, 11 and 12 months.

Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour between gender

Analysis was carried out using Mann Whitney U-test. Table 6 represents the results of comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviors between genders. The results indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in the frequency of gestures and verbal behaviors between genders.

Correlation between the presence of gestures and verbal behaviour in children

The data were further analysed using Pearson's correlation to verify if there was any significant correlation between the presence of gestures and verbal behaviour in children. Table 7 depicts the correlation coefficients between the different gestures

and verbal behaviours (using Pearson's Correlation). The analysis depicted a statistically significant correlation between expressive gestures and metaphoric gestures with verbal behaviours. The other types of gestures did not have a statistically significant correlation with the occurrence of verbal behaviours. The correlation of these two parameters with verbal behaviours is depicted in Figures 1 and 2. A strong negative correlation was obtained between the presence of expressive gestures and metaphoric gestures with verbal behaviours.

Discussion

This study was carried out to observe the development of gestures and early words in typically developing children. The study found that children use non-verbal gestures to communicate as early as 10 months, predating language development. Literature also provides evidence that gesture development antecedents early verbal behavior, with children typically producing their first gestures between 9 and 12 months (7, 8).

Infants begin communication through gestures and vocalisations, and later with words (23-25). Both gestures and speech play a significant role in children's communication (26). Infants use gestures at around nine months, both imperatively and declaratively (7). They use gesture-word combinations easily before using two-words together (27). Gestures help express thoughts when people are unable to speak, even children with developmental disabilities (28). They also facilitate word finding when additional information is needed (29). Iverson and colleagues (in 2005) indicated that mothers of children with expressive language deficits produce additional utterances embracing gestures (1).

The study institutes that expressive gestures are the most common type of gestures in infants, followed by metaphoric gestures. Infants use expressive gestures like smiling, clapping, and eye contact to convey their emotions and needs. Smiling and eye gaze were the most common expressive gestures observed. Research has shown that infants as young as six months old use gestures for social exchanges and expressing emotions. The interactions between parents and infants during infancy contribute to the development of expressive gestures, with eye gaze and smiling being the most common. Additionally, infants exhibit a higher proportion of expressions when they are visually and verbally engaged with both their mother and an object (30).

The study constructs that children, except for beat gestures, exhibited all types of gestures, which emerge from 12 months of age. Beat gestures are rhythmic movements and are linked to language development (10). Literature also has evidence stating that beat gestures are linked to language development and are

generally noticed only during the emergence of sentence-like utterances in children (31, 32). Verbal behaviors, including vocalizations, non-meaningful utterances, and meaningful words, are observed in children between 10 and 12 months. Mother's consistency and focus on verbal communication and interaction led to infant's considerable reliance on responding with actions on objects and with vocalizations (33). Children demonstrate imitative and non-meaningful words before meaningful words, predominantly nouns belonging to the category of names of family members (e.g.: /appa/, /amma/, /thatha/, /kaka/, /akka/, /papa/) (13). Preverbal productions, including onomatopoeic sounds, vocalizations, and communicative grunts, are predominantly produced in children in the prelinguistic stage. Hariharan and colleagues in 2018 demonstrated that typically developing Tamil speaking children produced early meaningful words at around 13 months of age. The words were bisyllabic and predominantly included nouns (18).

The study found no significant differences in the frequency of gestures and verbal behavior across ages and genders, suggesting that gesture development begins before 10 months and continues during early linguistic development. However, a negative correlation was found between expressive and metaphoric gestures and verbal behavior, suggesting a link between the usage of gestures paving way for vocabulary development. Acredolo and colleagues in 1988, and LeBarton and colleagues in 2015 provided evidence that children use gestures to ask things in their early childhood and later initiates the usage of true words and the use of gesture fades off gradually (5, 34).

Summary and Conclusion

This study was carried out to observe the development of gestures and early words in typically developing children. The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Analyse presence of gestures in children between 10 and 12 months of age
2. Describe verbal behaviour in children between 10 and 12 months of age
3. a) Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour across age
b) Comparison of frequency of gestures and verbal behaviour between genders
4. Correlation between the presence of gestures and verbal behaviour in children

This study included 30 participants who were typically developing children aged between 10, 11 and 12 months along with their primary caretaker. A video recording of the free play between the child and the

caretaker was done and the interaction and responses of the child was analysed and documented. The appearance of gestures, early words and verbal behaviour was coded using ELAN software (EUDICO Linguistic Annotator). The results were subjected to statistical analysis and the following was inferred.

1. Children exhibit a variety of gestures between 10 to 12 months of age. Amongst the gestures, expressive gestures and metaphoric gestures were the most commonly present gestures.
2. Beat gestures were observed to be emerging only from 12 months of age.
3. Verbal behaviours such as laryngeal grunting, vocalizations, imitative words, and non-meaningful words were observed in children between 10 and 12 months of age.
4. Production of words showed an increasing trend from 10 to 12 months. Children produced imitative and non -meaningful words before producing meaningful words. Meaningful words were observed in children from the age of 11 months.
5. The comparison of frequency of gestures across ages and between genders were not statistically significant.
6. Correlation of expressive gestures and metaphoric gestures was found to be significant with that of verbal behaviours.
7. Smiling and eye gaze was the most frequently used gesture type seen in infants during the mother child interaction.

Implications of the study

The findings of this study highlight the importance of considering language and gesture development as a socio cultural phenomenon. Speech and gesture are an inter-connected system, the study of gestures in development evolves as natural extensions of research on language development. Gestures and verbal behaviours observed in children exposed to Tamil as the primary language have been described in this study. This study also analysed the correlation between presence of gestures and onset of verbal behaviours and highlighted the correlation of expressive gestures and metaphoric gestures with development of verbal behaviours. An understanding of the role of gestures, early words and verbal behaviour on language development in typically developing children can pave the way to future application in early identification of developmental disabilities and training children with special needs.

Future directions of the study

This study can be done in younger age group i.e. less than 10 months of age to study on the development of gestures and early vocalisations of the infant. This study can also be done to analyse the correlation between verbal behaviour and language development in children older than 12 months. A longitudinal study tracking the development will throw more light in understanding the transition from prelinguistic development to language learning. This study can be carried out in children with special needs to understand the difference in language development from typically developing children.

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